

Training and Mentoring in Video Content Creation for Digital Marketing for Bika and Pinyaram Micro-Business Owners in Kayu Tanam District

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2025, 28(02), 857-864

Publication history: Received on 29 September 2025; revised on 05 November 2025; accepted on 07 November 2025

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2025.28.2.3641>

Abstract

The development of digital technology has transformed conventional marketing patterns into more effective and far-reaching social media-based ones. However, most micro-businesses in Kayu Tanam District, Padang Pariaman Regency, still rely on traditional promotion methods, thus suboptimal competitiveness of local products, particularly Bika and Pinyaram. This community service activity aims to improve the digital capacity of these entrepreneurs through training and mentoring in creating video content for digital marketing. The method used is a participatory approach with stages of socialization, technical training, mentoring, evaluation, and the formation of a sustainability community. Participants were trained to create promotional videos using smartphones and simple editing applications such as CapCut and InShot. The results of the activity showed a significant increase in digital skills and business confidence. All participants successfully produced and uploaded promotional content to Instagram, TikTok, and Facebook. The tangible impact was seen in increased interaction with consumers and a 50% increase in daily sales turnover. Furthermore, the Kayu Tanam Business Actors Digital Community was formed as a forum for collaboration and program sustainability. This activity demonstrates that simple technology-based training can be an effective strategy in empowering local MSMEs. With the continuous implementation of digital marketing, Bika and Pinyaram businesses have the potential to expand their market while strengthening the identity of traditional Minangkabau culinary in the digital economy era.

Keywords: Devotion; Marketing; Digital; Content; Video

1. Introduction

The development of digital technology in the last decade has brought fundamental changes in various sectors of life, including the business world and the creative economy [1-3]. Digital transformation changes the way people interact, communicate, and even transact. In the business context, marketing strategies no longer rely on conventional methods such as direct sales, brochures, or word-of-mouth marketing, but have shifted towards digital marketing that utilizes social media and online platforms as the main means of promotion [4-6]. This shift requires business actors of various scales, especially micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs), to adapt to remain competitive amidst changes in consumer behavior and increasing intensity of global market competition [7-10].

The increasing use of the internet and smart devices has changed people's consumption patterns. According to We Are Social data, more than 212 million Indonesians are connected to the internet, and 89% of them actively use social media to search for product information and conduct online transactions [11]. This condition shows that digital presence is no longer an optional option, but rather a strategic necessity for businesses to maintain their business sustainability. The ability to adapt to digital marketing is now a crucial indicator in maintaining the existence of MSMEs [12-19].

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One area with significant potential but facing challenges in digitalization is Kayu Tanam District in Padang Pariaman Regency, West Sumatra. This area is known as a production center for traditional Minangkabau food, particularly Bika and Pinyaram. Both products are typical cakes with high cultural value and promising economic opportunities as superior regional souvenirs. Its strategic location along the Padang-Bukittinggi highway is a crucial factor, as the area is frequently visited by tourists and local residents traveling between cities.

However, based on surveys and interviews conducted by the Universitas Negeri Padang community service team in early 2025, it was found that most micro-businesses in Kayu Tanam still rely on traditional marketing strategies. Most businesses simply wait for buyers to come directly to their sales outlets without actively promoting through digital media. This situation limits their market reach, especially on weekdays when visitor traffic is low.

Field data in Table 1 shows that the average sales turnover for business owners on weekdays ranges from IDR 200,000–IDR 400,000 per day, while on weekends it can increase to IDR 400,000–IDR 700,000. However, the actual potential revenue could reach IDR 700,000–IDR 1,000,000 per day if promotions are carried out consistently through digital channels. Furthermore, approximately 75% of the 27 business owners surveyed do not yet have business social media accounts such as Facebook, Instagram, TikTok, or YouTube. The main obstacles identified include a lack of digital knowledge and skills, limited content production resources (cameras, lighting, applications), and low awareness of the long-term benefits of digital marketing.

Table 1 Average Turnover Obtained by Bika and Pinyaram Micro Business Actors in Kayu Tanam District

Information	Price Normal (IDR/Day)	End Week (IDR /Day)	Potential Ordinary (IDR/Day)	Potential Weekend (IDR/Day)
Sales Turnover	200,000 – 400,000	400,000 – 700,000	400,000 - 700,000	700,000 – 1,000,000

In fact, several studies show that video content is one of the most effective forms of promotion in the digital era. A Wyzowl (2024) report states that 91% of global businesses use video as a primary marketing tool, and 87% of them experienced increased sales after implementing a video marketing strategy [20-22]. Video content is considered more engaging, memorable, and able to build emotional connections with consumers compared to text- or image-based promotions. Platforms like TikTok, Instagram Reels, Facebook, and YouTube allow micro-businesses to reach thousands of users simply by relying on creativity and consistent uploads, often without significant costs.

This phenomenon demonstrates that video-based marketing presents a significant opportunity for Bika and Pinyaram micro-enterprises in Kayu Tanam to expand their market and enhance their product competitiveness. By showcasing their distinctive manufacturing processes, unique local ingredients, and customer testimonials in video format, businesses can build a strong product image and increase consumer trust. Furthermore, this strategy aligns with global marketing trends that emphasize storytelling, product authenticity, and engaging visual communication.

Based on these conditions, the community service team from the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri Padang, implemented a Multidisciplinary Community Partnership (PMKM) program, with the main activity being training and mentoring in video content creation for digital marketing. This activity aims to address the challenge of low digital literacy among micro-entrepreneurs and increase their capacity to manage social media effectively. This program focuses not only on improving technical skills but also on empowering a digital entrepreneurial mindset, namely how entrepreneurs can think creatively, adaptively, and market-oriented.

This training is designed comprehensively, encompassing socialization, technical training, content production support, and publication on digital platforms. Through a participatory approach, business owners are encouraged to actively participate in every step of the process, ensuring that the results truly meet their needs.

With this training and mentoring, it is hoped that business actors can:

- Master basic digital technology skills, including creating, editing, and publishing promotional videos using a smartphone.
- Utilizing social media strategically as the main means of marketing local products.
- Increase self-confidence and digital independence, so that you no longer depend on traditional promotions.

- Develop creative content that is relevant to market trends, strengthens product image, and attracts consumer interest.
- Increase turnover and expand market networks, both locally, regionally and online.

Overall, this initiative is expected to provide a concrete solution to the low technological adaptability of the MSME sector, while simultaneously encouraging the digital transformation of the local economy. With the right mastery of information technology, Bika and Pinyaram micro-entrepreneurs will not only be able to survive but also thrive in the digital economy era. Furthermore, the success of this initiative has the potential to strengthen the identity of traditional Minangkabau culinary as a superior regional product capable of competing in the modern market through digital innovation.

2. Methods

This community service activity uses a participatory and applied approach, involving Bika and Pinyaram micro-entrepreneurs in Kayu Tanam District as active partners in every stage of the activity. This participatory approach was chosen so that participants are not merely training participants but also subjects directly involved in the learning, practice, and evaluation process.

The implementation of activities includes four main stages, namely:

- Socialization regarding the importance of digital marketing and the potential of social media as a promotional tool,
- Technical training in creating promotional video content using smartphones and simple editing applications such as CapCut and InShot,
- Assistance in the process of producing and uploading videos to digital platforms, as well as
- Evaluation of results and planning for program sustainability.

During the program, the community service team provided hands-on guidance through field practice, technical demonstrations, and individual mentoring tailored to the participants' needs. Evaluation was conducted through observation, interviews, and simple analysis of digital skill improvement, content upload consistency, and changes in sales turnover before and after the program. The results of this evaluation served as the basis for developing follow-up strategies and establishing a digital community of entrepreneurs to ensure the program's sustainability.

3. Results

3.1. Implementation of Activities

This community service activity was held from August to September 2025 in Kayu Tanam District, Padang Pariaman Regency, West Sumatra. Six micro-entrepreneurs participated, all of whom were producers and sellers of traditional Bika and Pinyaram foods. The activity involved two resource persons:

- Lecturer from the Faculty of Economics and Business, Universitas Negeri Padang (UNP) who provided material on digital marketing strategies, small business management, and the importance of product branding.
- Winda Apriyanti, a food blogger and content creator from Padang City, provides practical training on simple photography and videography techniques using smartphones, as well as strategies for attracting audiences through creative content on social media.

The activities are carried out in four main stages, namely:

- Socialization of the importance of digital marketing;
- Technical training in making promotional videos;
- Direct practical assistance in making and uploading videos; and
- Evaluation of results and measurement of the impact of activities.

All stages went according to plan, with high enthusiasm from participants who had never previously participated in digital marketing training.

3.2. Training and Mentoring Results

Training and mentoring activities produce real achievements in improving participant competency, which can be grouped into the following aspects.

3.2.1. Technical Skills Improvement

All participants successfully produced 30–60-second promotional videos using simple smartphones. The resulting videos showcased the uniqueness of the products, from the manufacturing process to the presentation of Bika and Pinyaram. Despite their simplicity, the results met basic digital promotion standards, such as good lighting, stable framing, and a concise, engaging narrative.

Participants will also be able to perform simple video editing using applications like CapCut and InShot. This skill is crucial because it allows entrepreneurs to create content independently without relying on external parties.

3.2.2. Utilization of Social Media as a Marketing Channel

Prior to this activity, 75% of participants did not have business social media accounts. After the mentoring, all participants had and were actively managing accounts on platforms like Instagram, TikTok, Facebook, and WhatsApp Business. They began consistently uploading promotional videos, product photos, and customer testimonials, as seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Digital Marketing Photos on Partner Social Media

Several participants reported increased interaction on social media, in the form of likes, comments, and direct messages from potential customers asking about product prices and availability.

3.3. Increased Digital Literacy and Self-Confidence

Before the program, most participants considered digital marketing difficult and expensive. After the training, they experienced significant improvements in their understanding of digital marketing concepts, use of social media applications, and confidence in creating and publishing content.

Participants also began to understand the importance of branding, storytelling, and the use of hashtags to expand promotional reach.

3.4. Consistency of Content Production

As a result of the mentoring, participants committed to creating at least two promotional videos per week. This demonstrates a behavioral shift from passive entrepreneurs to active content creators. This commitment also serves as the first step in building long-term engagement with audiences and maintaining product visibility on digital platforms.

3.5. Impact of Activities on Partner Businesses

Based on the results of observations and follow-up interviews, this activity has had a measurable positive impact on partner businesses, both in terms of marketing, management, and economics.

3.5.1. Improving Professionalism and Product Image

After the event, participants' social media presence became more professional and engaging. Promotional content was no longer random, but had a focused narrative, with a uniform and consistent visual tone.

The image of Bika and Pinyaram products has improved in the eyes of consumers, because they now appear with more modern visual quality and packaging without abandoning traditional values.

3.5.2. Increased Turnover and Market Reach

Participants reported increased sales, particularly on weekdays that were previously quiet. Based on a comparison of pre- and post-activity data:

- (1) Day normal: turnover increases from IDR 200,000–IDR 400,000 to IDR 400,000–IDR 700,000 per day.
- (2) Weekend: turnover increased from IDR 400,000–IDR 700,000 to IDR 700,000–IDR 1,000,000 per day.

In addition to increased direct sales, participants also began receiving online orders via WhatsApp Business and private messages on social media, which had not previously been the case.

3.5.3. Formation of a Digital Micro Business Community

As a follow-up to the activity, participants formed the Timber Plantation Business Actors Digital Community, which serves as a platform for sharing knowledge, sharing content, and assisting each other in the promotional process. This community strengthens networks among business actors and fosters a spirit of collaboration.

4. Discussion

The results of the activity demonstrated that simple technology-based training with an intensive mentoring approach proved highly effective in improving the digital competency of micro-entrepreneurs. Through this approach, participants not only gained new knowledge but also experienced a contextual learning process tailored to their business needs and circumstances. This activity successfully fostered a new awareness among entrepreneurs that digital marketing is not complicated, but rather a skill that can be learned and applied using tools they already have, such as smartphones.

The main success factors of this activity lie in three important aspects:

- A participatory approach, where participants are actively involved in every stage of the activity, from planning and training to practice and evaluation. This direct involvement creates a sense of ownership over the process and outcomes, thus increasing participants' motivation to implement the acquired skills in their own businesses.
- A combination of theory and hands-on practice helps participants understand digital marketing concepts and apply them concretely. This approach has proven to be more effective than lectures alone, as participants can immediately see the results of their work through the video content they produce.
- A collaboration between academics and practitioners, combining the scientific insights of lecturers with the empirical experience of content creators and digital marketers. This synergy produces learning that is relevant, applicable, and aligned with the real needs of business actors in the field.

These findings align with research [7-12], which confirms that digital marketing training and mentoring can improve the skills, competitiveness, and income of micro-entrepreneurs. Furthermore, Wyzowl's report also confirms that video marketing strategies have been shown to increase sales conversions by up to two times compared to conventional text-

or image-based promotional methods [20-22]. This demonstrates that this type of training is not only relevant but also well-targeted in meeting the needs of entrepreneurs in the digital era.

Furthermore, this activity has had a significant impact on empowering the local economy. Prior to the program, Bika and Pinyaram businesses relied solely on on-site sales and tourist traffic. After participating in the training, they began actively managing their businesses' social media accounts and consistently promoting their products online. This opened up new market opportunities, not only locally but also regionally through the increasing number of online orders.

Beyond the economic impact, this activity also has positive social implications. Micro-entrepreneurs, particularly women who dominate the traditional culinary sector, now have a newfound confidence in using technology. They no longer view social media as complicated, but as a tool for economic empowerment that can be mastered. The collaborative, practice-based learning process helps narrow the digital divide between urban and rural entrepreneurs.

The success of this activity also confirms that digital transformation for MSMEs doesn't always require significant capital, but can begin with practical training focused on basic skills, creativity, and consistent implementation. The use of smartphones and free apps like CapCut and InShot is clear evidence that limited resources are not a barrier to innovation if accompanied by a willingness to learn and the right mentoring support.

From an academic perspective, this activity contributes to the development of a community-based digital empowerment model, combining non-formal education, digital technology, and social entrepreneurship. This model has proven effective in improving digital literacy among regional businesses and strengthening the relationship between universities and the community. This collaborative approach also reflects the concrete implementation of the Tridharma Perguruan Tinggi (Three Pillars of Higher Education), particularly in the aspect of solution-oriented and sustainable community service.

Thus, this training not only results in improved technical skills but also creates behavioral and mindset changes among business actors regarding the importance of digital innovation. This empowerment is sustainable, as participants now have the skills and confidence to continuously adapt to technological developments and market trends. In the long term, this activity is expected to strengthen the local creative economy ecosystem and expand the contribution of MSMEs to regional economic growth.

5. Conclusion

The training and mentoring program for creating video content for digital marketing for Bika and Pinyaram micro-entrepreneurs in Kayu Tanam District was successfully implemented and has had a significant impact on improving the digital capacity of micro-entrepreneurs. Based on the results of the activity and the evaluation, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- Improving digital and creative skills of business actors.
 - All participants successfully mastered the basic skills of creating and editing promotional videos using simple devices (smartphones and free apps). They were able to produce engaging 30–60-second video content worthy of social media publication.
- Transformation of marketing patterns from conventional to digital.
 - Previously, most businesses relied solely on direct sales at their locations. After this activity, all participants actively used social media platforms like TikTok, Instagram, Facebook, and WhatsApp Business as their primary promotional tools.
- Increased digital literacy and self-confidence.
 - Businesses have shown significant changes in their understanding of the importance of digital marketing, hashtag use, storytelling, and active customer engagement through online platforms.
- Positive economic impact.
 - Sales turnover has increased, especially on weekdays when there were previously few customers. Average revenue has risen from IDR 200,000–IDR 400,000 to IDR 400,000–IDR 700,000 per day on weekdays, and from IDR 400,000–IDR 700,000 to IDR 700,000–IDR 1,000,000 per day on weekends.
- Strengthening social networks and local collaboration.
 - This activity established the Digital Community of Planted Timber Business Actors, which serves as a platform for sharing knowledge and supporting the program's sustainability. This community strengthens collaboration between business actors and provides a platform for post-training self-help.

Thus, this community service activity not only successfully improved the technical skills of business actors but also fostered an adaptive mindset toward digital technology developments. This program serves as a concrete example of the role of higher education institutions in supporting technology-based community economic empowerment. To maintain the sustainability of the impact of activities and expand their benefits, several suggestions that can be put forward are as follows:

- For Business Actors (Partners)
 - Still maintain consistency in creating and uploading video content regularly (at least twice a week) so that social media algorithms continue to increase the reach of product promotions.
 - Developing creativity in storytelling and product branding, by highlighting local values and the uniqueness of the traditional taste of Bika and Pinyaram.
 - Integrate digital marketing strategies with offline promotions, such as listing social media accounts on product packaging, banners, or customer business cards.
- For Regional Governments and Related Institutions
 - Regular advanced training programs covering digital branding, simple financial management, and marketplace access are needed to help entrepreneurs advance.
 - Local governments can facilitate partnerships with local and national e-commerce platforms, so that superior regional products can penetrate wider markets.
 - Encourage collaboration between business actors, academics, and the private sector to form a sustainable digital economic ecosystem at the village and district levels.
- For Universities and Community Service Teams
 - Similar community service activities need to be continued with a more specific thematic focus, such as online store management, digital content performance analysis, and technology-based financial literacy.
 - Long-term support is needed to measure the economic impact sustainably and help businesses adapt to changing digital trends.
 - Model This training can be used as a prototype for replicative community service activities for other regions that have similar micro-business characteristics, so that its benefits can be expanded nationally.

Compliance with ethical standards

Acknowledgements

The authors would like to thank Lembaga Penelitian dan Pengabdian Masyarakat Universitas Negeri Padang for funding this work with a contract number: 2219/UN35.15/PM/2025.

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